

SYNTHESIS OF DININIC ACID*

BY BIDYUT KAMAL BHATTACHARYYA

The sodio derivative of ethyl 2-methyl-2 : 3-dicyano-propane-3-carboxylate on treatment with β -ethoxy ethyl iodide furnishes ethyl 2-methyl-2 : 3-dicyano-pentane-5-ethoxy-3-carboxylate which on hydrolysis gives dininic acid.

Kir'yalov (*J. Gen. Chem. U.S.S.R.*, 1938, 8, 740 ; 1939, 9, 401, 432) has obtained a lactonic acid (dininic acid) by the degradation of biglandulinic acid isolated from the juice of *Euphorbia Biglandulosa*. The author has conclusively proved from analytical data that dininic acid should possess the structure (I)

In the following lines has been described a method by which the synthetical confirmation of the above structure has been achieved.

Acetone cyanohydrin has been condensed with ethyl sodio-cyanoacetate in alcoholic solution and then β -ethoxy ethyl iodide is allowed to react on the resulting compound *in situ* according to the method of Thorpe and Higson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 1455) when (II) is obtained. The pentane derivative (II) is hydrolysed by heating with concentrated hydrochloric acid in acetic acid solution in a sealed tube, when the elimination of carbon dioxide and lactonisation occur simultaneously to yield (I). It is crystallised from petroleum ether and chloroform, m.p. 129-31.5°. Dininic acid, obtained by the degradation of the natural product, melts at 129-31°.

* A note was published in *Science & Culture*, 1042-43, 8, 309.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 2-Methyl-2 : 3-dicyano-pentane-5-ethoxy-3-carboxylate (II).— β -Ethoxy ethyl iodide (66 g.) was added to sodio derivative of ethyl 2-methyl-2 : 3-dicyano-propane-3-carboxylate prepared from acetone cyanohydrin (28 g. in 20 c.c. alcohol) and ethyl sodio-cyanoacetate (sodium, 7.1g., ethyl cyanoacetate, 36.6 g. and alcohol, 114 c.c.) according to Thorpe and Higson (*loc. cit.*) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 36 hours. It was next diluted with water, extracted with benzene and distilled, b.p. 152.4°/6.5 mm., yield 14 g. (Found : C, 61.8 ; H, 8.06. $C_{12}H_{20}O_5N_2$, requires C, 61.9 ; H, 7.93 per cent).

γ -Lactone of *2-Methylpentane-5-ol-2 : 3-dicarboxylic acid* (I).—The above condensation product (5.5 g.) was heated in a sealed tube with a mixture of hydrochloric (*d* 1.19, 20 c.c.) and acetic (16 c.c.) acids at 175-85° for 10 hours. The reaction mixture was diluted with a small quantity of water and thoroughly extracted with ether. The ether was driven off and the residue solidified on keeping under vacuum. It was first crystallised from acetone in which it was readily soluble and then from a mixture of petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) and chloroform. The acid, on heating, shrinks at 129° and melts at 130-31.5°. (Found : C, 56.05 ; H, 6.5. $C_6H_{11}O_4$, requires C, 55.81 ; H, 6.97 per cent).

The above lactonic acid (1.4551 g.) furnished a cinchonidine salt when treated with cinchonidine (2.4872 g.) in aqueous (6 c.c.) methanol (20 c.c.) and allowed to stand for several hours. The salt was crystallised several times from dilute methanol, m.p. 183°. (Found ; C, 69.38 ; H, 7.32. $C_{11}H_{13}O_4$, $C_{11}H_{13}ON_2$, requires C, 69.3 ; H, 7.25 per cent).

My grateful thanks are due to Prof. P. C. Mitter for his valuable advice and keen interest during the progress of this work. My thanks are also due to Mr. N. Ghosh for micro-analysis of the compounds.